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Socioeconomic effects of corruption on Nigeria's Southwest Institutions

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Abstract

It becomes worrisome when corruption meddles in the process of human capital formation as it is seen playing out in higher institutions of learning which is not insulated from the larger society. This study employs Organizational Culture Theories to examine the socioeconomic effects of corruption on Nigeria's Southwest institutions. The study measured socioeconomic effect of corruption with corruption on students' academic performance and corruption on students' admission process. The study adopted descriptive survey research design and primary data extracted with the aid of structured questionnaire designed in a four Likert scale manner to extract information from purposively selected higher institutions of learning in the Southwest, Nigeria. The population of the study is 124, 929. This study employs scientific sampling technique determination of Krejcie and Morgan (1970) that recommends a sample size of 382 for a population below 1million. Ordinary least square regression analysis was employed to analyse the data. The study revealed that corruption on students' academic performance and corruption on students' admission process have positive correlation and significant effects on corruption in Southwest institutions of learning in Nigeria. Based on these findings, the study concludes that corrupt practices by all academic stakeholder on admission process and academic performance jointly aggravate corruption in southwest higher institution of learning. The study recommends that Federal and State Government should evolve a conference marking system which compartmentalizes markers and checkers while encouraging whistleblowing within the higher institutions community. Study also recommends for realtime examination and admission as lag period between examination and admission encourages corrupt practices of racketeering.

Keywords: Admission Process; Human Capital Formation; Organizational Culture Theories

1. Introduction

Higher institutions of learning world over are the engine room that provides the needed human capital formation by which the society is driven. Such that the quality the labour force, structural transformation of the society, technological development, production of future leaders levels of entrepreneurial development, civility and ethical standard of the society are all greatly influenced by products of her higher institution of learning. It is then worrisome, when corrupt practices that play out in the larger society infiltrate the educational system this is so because the educational sectors have remarkable capacity to set in motion an uncontrollable reproductive process of corruption in the larger society and thereby twist the development of structures of a nation. So alarming is the reproductive process of corruption in the larger society by the educational system that Nigeria was ranked 149 of 180 countries surveyed on corruption perception index in 2020 (Transparency International, 2020).

The educational system is the conduit through which an individual or group of persons in the system are inculcated with attitudes and abilities that are considered to have values and relevance by which the society becomes gainfully developed alongside individual or group of person. So much so then, that higher level education is considered to be an

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instrument of social change and economic development. Higher institutions of learning, particularly the Universities, are set up to train the nation's youth to become resourceful human capital, patriotic, responsible and dependable future leaders with impeccable moral and professional standards. Regrettably, large numbers of students admitted to these institutions turned out to become variant, wayward, irresponsible, unpatriotic and unreliable citizens through their involvement in corrupt practices (Jekayinfa&Kolawole, 2010).

Corruption is the projection of self, clannish or primordial interest against and above overall interest of the society. It discourages individuals from fully investing in tertiary education and pursuing it to the end because there is no opportunity offered to them to benefit from these long-term investments (Sen, 2015). Corruption erodes incentives that motivate young people to work hard while teaching them that there are easier ways to achieve success (Rumyantseva, 2005). Corruption in the Nigeria public domain goes beyond looting of revenues accruing to nations but extended to loans on both genuine and spurious ground. The socio-economic effects of corruption on Nigeria's Southwest Institutions could be seen from prevailing corrupt practices that underline activities of stakeholders in higher institutions; the parents, the lecturers, the management and also the students such that parents fraudulent front to get their children admitted through unscrupulous academic, non academic or go between agents while student also sustain themselves through higher learning by been shielded by cultism.

Higher education student corruption could be academic corruption or non academic corruption of which same is applicable to all other possible players in higher institution corruption loop; students, lecturers, administrators, depending on the hierarchy so occupied. Students academic corruption could be seen in examination and admission racketeering, drug abuse, indecent dressing, abortion, purchasing term papers/essays, impersonation, paying bribes for grades, copying into an exam, using girls to sort lecturers via lecture's handle, collusion, machinery, cheating on tests, copying from someone else's examination answer book, stealing a test, university document forgery, plagiarism acts while the student non academic corruption span across unionism, naija sporting bets, hostel run and cultism.

Another form of corruption of with socioeconomic effect on higher learning institution, reputed as the epicenter of corruption is the admission process with both the Joint. Admission Matriculation Board and the Universities take the admission process as a source of internal revenue that worth being politicized and competed for. The admission process has become a gaming racket that involves, parents, lecturers, non academic staff alongside other connected student or cult students fronting as go-between to secure admission for prospective students. The incoming students take note of all these perverted admission processes which mostly ended up denying qualified and eligible students in favour of the unqualified but privileged individual

Furthermore, higher institution examination and students academic performance has also being fingered as a corruption loop that contains many vested stakeholders; parents, lecturers, non academic, students, business centres and examination machineries of hired to write examinations, tests or assignment in order to be graded while some students may not even bother appear for such and yet could still be seen graded aright. Examinations malpractice with its shortcuts could possibly lure some students into other areas of misconducts such drugs trafficking, prostitutions, phornography, yahoo yahoo (cybercrime), armed, blackmailing all in a bid to make money to pay for scores (Adewale, 2014; Uzochukwu, 2015). The worrisome aspect could be seen in the populated unskilled labour of applicants churned out by the higher learning institutions rated unfit by employers of labour. The reproductive processes of corrupt practices by institution of learning which keep churning disappointing results and has necessitated the called for the creation of skills enhancement zones whereby public and private sectors and academia could collaborate on the design and implementation of workforce development plans for various industries.

The disorderliness of corruption could be seen manifesting both among undergraduates and postgraduates students. The socio economic effects of these acts further endanger higher institution of learning. The arrays of stakeholders involved in corrupt practices across higher institutions could possibly have made corruption systemic with the involvement of parents. The predicting roles of parents in fuelling corrupt practices of their wards on campuses of higher institutions of learning cannot be downplayed as their wards brought through the backdoor into the higher institutions of learning runs the networks of corruptions, property and lives destruction, to admission racketeering, recruitment cartel, prostitutions, robberies and all violent crimes

In the majority of studies that investigate corruption on higher institution of learning are mostly country specific studies Seniwoliba and Boahene, 2015 (Ghana); of Nigeria was the works of Nmadu and Khalil (2017); United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2017); United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2017); Nmadu and Khalil (2017); Ajitoni and Olaniyan (2018); Ogu and Amakwe (2020). While, to the extent of literature review, there exist dearth of region specific studies, as Abdu-Raheem (2020); Asiyai and Oghuvbu (2020). It is this dearth of literature that this present study will fill and expand the frontier of knowledge.

To achieve the objectives of this study, the following hypotheses are tested;

- H01: Corruption has no significant effect on students' academic performance in Nigeria's southwest institutions.
- H02: Corruption has no significant effect on students' admission process in Nigeria's southwest institutions.

2. Conceptual Framework

2.1. Higher Institutions of Learning

This concept is widely used to refer to post-secondary education, where a degree, diploma, or certificate is awarded at the end of study (Tella, 2008). According to the Encyclopaedia Britannica Concise defines higher education as Study beyond the level of secondary education. Institutions of higher education include not only colleges and universities but also professional schools in such fields as law, theology, medicine, business, music, and art. They also include teacher-training schools, community colleges, and institutes of technology. At the end of a prescribed course of study, a degree, diploma, or certificate is awarded.

2.2. Students' Academic Performance and Students' Admission Process

Corrupt practices are not necessarily new to the university system as the problem can be traced to the early days when lecturers pried open sealed envelopes to copy exam questions before sealing them back. Corruption in education is the pervasion of the expected standard of behaviour by those in authority in the educational system for their own personal gain to the detriments of others and the system in its pursuit of quality manpower and national development. Corruption in the system has made it easy for some scholars to posit that schools are no longer institutions of learning but instead as money exchange department to help (Okojie, 2012).

Hallak and Poisson (2007) defined corruption in higher education as the systematic use of public office for private benefit, whose impact is significant on the availability and quality of educational goods and services, and, as a consequence on access, quality or equity in education. This is because corruption erodes the core values of the educational process and thereby undermines and distorts human capital formation and, weakens social cohesion by engendering distrust in interpersonal and intergroup relation (Idoniboye-Obu, 2014).

2.3. Importance Of Anti Corruption Education in Nigeria

Pursuant to Section 6 of the Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Act 2000 which ICPC to carry out preventive, enforcement and enlightenment functions, hence anti-corruption education is very central in combating corrupt practices in higher institutions of learning. Anti-Corruption education is expected to give awareness and change to all the younger generation to understand and realize the importance of having the character of anti-corruption and stay above board even as corruption is considered a major disadvantage to development. Not only does corruption weaken human capital development, retard economic growth, constrict investment and undermines the rule of law, cost of corruption has been estimated by the World Economic to Forum to stand at about US\$2.6 trillion a year. The impacts of corruption disproportionately affect the most vulnerable people in society hence it becomes central to introduce anti-corruption education.

The importance of Anti -corruption education at all levels of learning could be seen in the effects it will give by evolving a firm rule of law with appropriate sanction against the rulers and the ruled, the corruption mechanism that will evolve to safeguard public administration and systems coupled with enthroning transparency and accountability from all duty bearers and rights holders, non-state actors, how it will heighten information awareness such that corruption that thrives in secrecy can be lightened up.

The importance of anti-corruption education teaching materials for the younger generation cannot be overemphasised particularly teaching materials in Social Studies with rich contents that contain the value of anti-corruption character as such is expected to give awareness and change to all the younger generation to understand and realize the importance of having the character of anti-corruption (Sarmini & Ulin, 2017).

The Anti-corruption education is not just a means for the transmission of knowledge, but also an emphasis on character formation, moral awareness and anti-corruption values in the resistance against corruption. Anti-corruption education is also a mechanism to develop study skills in capturing configuration problems and difficulties of nationality issues that triggered the corruption, the impact, prevention, and resolution (Open Society Initiative for West Africa, 2016).

The model of Anti-corruption education is expected to instill and disseminate anti-corruption values across all levels of learning, so they understand about it early that corruption is contrary to legal norms or religious norms. It is a good thing, if the government establishes the educational institution as a repair workshop of nation's morality. Educational institution is the right choice as the frontline formation of national character. In its application, there should be particular anti-corruption education materials in the curriculum at the primary level to college. Anti-corruption education emphasizes more on the moral formation of anti-corruption efforts than the transformation of knowledge and the ins and outs of anti-corruption theory to students.

Combating corruption requires the role of teachers/lecturers to begin serious in combating corruption. Efforts to eradicate corruption should be implemented as early as possible from the level of elementary school education up to the university level by implementing subjects or courses of anti-corruption education. Now is the time required for the development of the idea of learning a course of anti-corruption education for students of Primary School Teacher Education because the output is a teacher candidate who is expected later to provide understanding, planting, and delivering anti-corruption values to students. As the starting point to repair manners, the learning value investment of anti-corruption culture must start from the basic education level, though it certainly cannot be done in a short time. It is very likely that education is the only possible path most likely to be taken in order to provide public awareness (Indawati, 2015).

2.4. Empirical Review

2.4.1. Students' Academic Performance and Corruption

Boly et al. (2020) engaged thematic research approach to investigate the effects of corruption on educational quality and quantity. The study employed a simple model with corrupt and honest examiners, as well as applicants with heterogeneous innate ability. Findings from the study revealed that “strong” candidates rely only upon effort; “medium” candidates choose positive levels of both bribe and effort, while “weak” candidates rely only on bribery. Study submitted that corruption possibly lessen education quality by lowering aggregate effort level but increase education quantity by increasing the aggregate chances of obtaining a degree. Study was on effect of corruption on academic performance while this study further considers corruption on admission process to explain the socioeconomic impact of corruption in Nigeria Southwest higher institutions.

Asiyai and Oghuvbu (2020) adopted survey research design to interrogate the frequently committed crimes in Nigerian tertiary institutions and administrative strategies for its effective management. Study deployed stratified questionnaire to elicit data from nine tertiary institutions from southwest. Findings from the study showed that the common crime prevalent in tertiary institution in South-West Nigeria as examination malpractices, assault, plagiarism, sexual harassment, and certificate forgery. Study submitted the need for mounting of closed circuit camera in strategic locations, regular monitoring of activities, use of anti-cult group. Study submission of examination malpractices as crime typifies it as a serious corrupt practices and this further reinforced the need to investigate further the socioeconomic effect on Nigeria's southwest tertiary institutions

Atanda (2019) qualitatively examined corrupt acts in tertiary institutions and possible roadmap for management in Nigeria. The study employed thematic research design with reliance on related journals, extant literature, textbooks and print materials. Findings from the study emphasised that tertiary education contribution to national development via manpower training is being threatened by the corrupt practices among university staff and student which waters down sexual abuse, stealing, lack of accountability among others such that all these watered down credibility of the higher learning education with poor ranking among comity of nations. Study focused on corrupt practices that cast doubts on academic performance due to corruption while this study will engage more variables to measure socioeconomic effect of corruption on Nigeria Southwest institution.

Aniodoh et al. (2017) leveraged on mixed method research design to interrogate influence of academic corruption and students' achievement in tertiary institutions in Enugu State. The study employed purposive sampling was used in selecting the sample and data was elicited through questionnaire structured on a 4 likeart point scale. Data analysis was done using percentages and mean rating. Results from analysed data showed corrupt practices of paying for marks, extortion via textbooks and assignments, sex-for-marks and plagiarism have negative effect on the academic achievements of the students via bad study habit, lack of inspiration and motivation to work hard in and wrong perception of values in life among others. Study submitted that strategies adopted to curb corruption in the institutions are grossly inadequate hence the need to extend the whistle blowing strategy to greatly assist in exposing corrupt and incompetent staff as well as unserious students. Study was state focused while this study will focus on Southwest region in Nigeira thereby expanding scope of observation

Oko and Adie (2016) employed structured questionnaire to interrogate effects of examination malpractice and solution to curb the Menace in Cross River University of technology. The study administered 250 randomly distributed questionnaires to elicit data from relevant stakeholders. result from the study showed that examination malpractices in higher institution do produce future leaders with low morale and inconsequential academic values, while always end up with unfulfilled dreams in their chosen career. The study focused on effects of examination malpractice of which this study goes beyond in measuring socioeconomic effects of corruption on Nigeria Southwest institutions. The study used Cross River State data of which present data will use regional data

Whawo (2015) adopted triangulation method to investigate existence of corrupt practices in all tertiary institutions in Delta State of Nigeria. The study employed random sampling technique to elicit data with open ended questionnaire in all the seven tertiary institutions in Delta State on students, academic and non academic staff. Findings of the study revealed that there exists corrupt practices in tertiary institutions particularly examination malpractices that extort money from study. Study submitted that this account for the high level of unskilled manpower churned out by tertiary institutions. The study though done with Delta State data majorly harped on examination malpractices while this study will use other constructs; recruitment corruption, cultism corruption and admission corruption to measure it socioeconomic effects on Nigeria's South west institutions.

2.4.2. Students' Admission Process and Corruption

Ogu and Amakwe (2020) in a thematic approach investigated possible recipe for combating corruption in Nigeria tertiary institutions. Study employed extant literature, related academic journals, and relevant publications. Findings from the study revealed that recruitment process into higher institution of learning hardly favour emergence of qualified personnel as most employment comes with cost string as favoritism, bribes, nepotism and payoffs in lecturers, hence such wrong foundation in employment process cannot but aggravate corrupt practices couple with low quality in instructional materials. The study focused on impact of corruption on recruitment and admission process while present study will consider in additional effects of cultism and examination corruption as it affects socioeconomic capabilities of Nigeria Southwest institutions.

Arop et al. (2018) employed factorial research design to examine the nexus between personnel management and corrupt academic practices in universities in Cross River State, Nigeria. Study employed purposive sampling technique to select 1200 and 200 students and lecturers respectively while instrument used for data collection was a 25-item rating scale. Findings from the study showed that that discipline and supervision of university students have a joint significant influence on university students' corrupt academic practices, with students' supervision having the most influence on corrupt academic practices. Study was of Delta State data on supervision process and corrupt practices which is in same manner as examination process while this study, of the Southwest region, intends to measure other construct of corrupt practices; recruitment process, admission process and cultism which the study did not consider

Seniwoliba and Boahene (2015) deployed qualitative research design underpinned by the rational choice theory to investigate expression of corruption in higher education and the roles of the university administrator in Ghana. The study employed thematic approach with reliance on Ghanaian policy documents, experiential knowledge drawn decade of personal experience as administrator, extant literature and relevant journals in order to draw conclusion. Findings of the study submitted that corruption in higher institution manifest through admissions, procurement, appointment, academic dishonesty and favoritism. Study concluded that government should close up the gap between the professor and the office clerk with urgent attention to the Ghanaian moral values. This study, though Ghana specific, did not relate cultism as an act of corruption of which present study does in examining the socioeconomic effect of corruption on Nigeria Southwest higher institutions

2.5. Theoretical Framework

2.5.1. Organizational Culture Theories

Organizational culture theories deal with corruption at the meso or intermediate level of the organization in which the agent is located. This group of theories assumes that corruption results from a mental state instilled in individuals by group culture and not from faulty character or wrong morality. Organizational culture theories position contradicts both public choice and bad apple theories as it sets out to seek to account for the context that produces corrupt behaviour as against a focus on the individual corrupt agent. Organizational theories seek to describe the conditions under which corruption may occur but are unable to account for why particular individuals - and not others - are corrupt. They simply assume that people in organizations act on the particular dynamics of the organization (De Graaf, 2007).

In applying organizational theory to cheating among students, Gallant and Drinan, argued that it provides a more robust framework for the analysis of student cheating problem by situating it in “the context of the educational institution as a complex organization affected by people, time, and social forces” (Gallant & Drinan, 2006). It conceives of educational institutions as complex organizations “because a number of different subgroups are central to its functioning. The theory opine further that organizational theory offers the best prospects for contextualizing the problem and suggesting management strategies that are conducive to more systemic organizational change. Viewing the problem through this lens helps move educational leaders beyond reacting to vested interests to creating generative responses for change (Gallant & Drinan, 2006).

3. Methodology

This study employs survey research design using descriptive statistics presentation. This study focuses on higher institutions of learning in the Southwest, Nigeria. The population for this study covers four purposively chosen institutions of learning mainly of universities across four States; Ekiti, Ondo, Oyo Osun States, out of the six States that make up the South West region. The total population both Staff and undergraduate students of these purposively selected higher institutions of learning stands 124,929. The population of this study is a finite population and is large; therefore, the entire population will not be studied. This study engaged scientific sampling technique determination of Krejcie and Morgan (1970) that suggests a sample size of 382 for a population above 75,000 but below 1 million.

A random sampling technique of the four purposively chosen higher institutions of learning was adopted while, the target respondents in each of the higher institutions of learning are: the undergraduate students (both fulltime and part time), post graduate students, non-academic staff, academic staff, students Union leaders; of departmental, faculty and institution as a whole,

Table 1 Population of Study

S/n	Institution	State	Staff	Students	Total
1	Obafemi Awolowo University- Ile Ife	OSUN	5, 694	35,906	41,600
2	Adekunle Ajasin University-Akungba	ONDO	2,050	22,850	24,900
3	Federal University, Oye	EKITI	2,384	7,792	10,186
4	University of Ibadan, Ibadan	OYO	7,500	41,743	48,243
	<i>GRAND TOTAL</i>				124,929

Source: Author’s Compilation, (2022).

This study adopted primary method of data collection through structured questionnaire to extract required data on a four points Likert-Scale of Strongly Agreed (SA) Agreed (A), Disagreed (DA) and Strongly Disagreed (SD). This study employed the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression technique to determine the socioeconomic effect of corruption on higher learning institutions in Southwest, Nigeria. The functional representation of the model for the study is given below;

The study will use multiple regression analysis to test the statistical significance of the independent variables on the dependent variables.

CSAP = Corruption on Students’ Academic Performance.

COSA = Corruption on Students’ Admission

The simple regression equation model for the study is given below

$$Y = f(\text{CSAP}, \text{COSA}) \dots \dots \dots \text{eq}(i)$$

Linearizing equation (1) above produces a simple regression model as thus:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{CSAP} + \beta_2 \text{COSA} + e \dots \dots \dots \text{eq}(ii)$$

Where; Y = Corruption in Southwest Institutions in Nigeria. (CSIN)

B_0 = is the constant or coefficient of intercept.

CSAP = Corruption on Students' Academic Performance.

COSA = Corruption on Students' Admission

β_1, β_2 = the corresponding coefficients for the respective dependent variables.

e = stochastic error term

Equation (ii) is estimated using the method of Ordinary Least Square to ascertain the coefficients β_1 through β_2 which measures the slope of each of the variables above. We shall introduce X_1 through X_2 to represent the variables as

CSAP = Corruption on Students' Academic Performance. = X_1

COSA = Corruption on Students' Admission = X_2

Reliability of the primary data was checked through Cronbach's alpha. Cronbach's alpha is most widely used method; which requires that there must be a satisfactory reliability value of more than 0.6 for the scale to be reliable (Cronbach, 1951). Cronbach value beyond ($\alpha = .7$) signifies acceptable reliability (Guieford, 1965).

Corruption on Students' Academic Performance (CSAP) revealed a Cronbach's Alpha (α) of 0.8959, while Corruption on Students' Admission Process (COSA) exhibited Cronbach's Alpha (α) of 0.8798 and the overall twenty one questions had Cronbach Alpha (α) of 0.8996. Since all the Cronbach's values are well above the 0.6 threshold, this then adjudged the measurement scales reliable as research instrument.

4. Results and Analysis of Data

Table 2 Correlation Coefficient Matrix

		CSIN	CSAP	COSA
CSIN	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	384		
CSAP	Pearson Correlation	0.791**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	384	384	
COSA	Pearson Correlation	0.789**	0.678**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	384	384	384

Source: Extract of SPSS Output, 2022.

Table 2 presents the correlation matrix of the relationship among the variables. It is observed that the variables correlate fairly well. The correlation matrix shows the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables in the model. The result reveals a positive correlation between corruption on students' academic performance (CSAP) and corruption in southwest institutions in Nigeria, with the coefficient value of 0.791 and a significant probability value of 0.003. This indicates that an increase in corruption on students' academic performance will translate to an increase corruption in southwest institutions in Nigeria. The relationship between corruption on students' admission process (COSA) and corruption in southwest institutions in Nigeria is also positive and significant because the coefficient correlation of COSA 0.789 with significant probability value of 0.003.

4.1. Test of Hypotheses

Table 3 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.972a	.957	.957	.10424	.957	2367.786	5	378	.003	.315

Source: Extract of SPSS Output, 2021.a. Predictors: (Constant), CSAP, COSAb. Dependent Variable: CSIN

The Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of 0.957 indicates that about 95% of corruption in Southwest institutions of learning is explained by corruption on students’ academic performance and corruption on students’ admission process, while remaining 5% are attributable to other independent variables that are not captured in the regression model. A Durbin Watson of .315 falls within the rule of thumb ranges.

4.2. Analysis of Variance

Table 4 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	128.634	3	25.727	2152.694	.000b
	Residual	4.107	378	.011		
	Total	132.741	383			

Source: Extract of SPSS Output, 2021; a. Dependent Variable: CSIN; b. Predictors: (Constant), CSAP, COSA

The F-Statistic of 2152.694 and its corresponding P-value of 0.003 indicates that the model is fit and the independent variables are properly selected, combined and used.

4.3. Multiple Regression Result

Table 5 Ordinary Least Square Regression Result

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.583	.040		14.736	.000		
	CSAP	.733	.041	.906	17.770	.000	.031	8.768
	COSA	.184	.037	.252	4.950	.000	.032	7.557

Dependent Variable: CSIN; Predictors: (Constant), CSAP, COSA; Source: Extract of SPSS Output, 2021.

5. Discussion of Findings

Analysis emanating from the study on hypothesis one is that corruption on students’ academic performance has a positive effect which is significant on corruption in southwest institutions in Nigeria. This explains that corruption on students’ academic performance will likely translate to an increase in corruption in southwest institutions in Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the findings in previous works of Boly, Keita, Okara and Okou (2020); Asiyai and Oghuvbu (2020); Atanda (2019); AniodohEbouh and Nweke (2017); Oko and Adie (2016);Whawo (2015).

The outcome of this study from hypothesis two is that corruption on students’ admission process has significant and positive effect on corruption in southwest institutions in Nigeria. Corrupt practices bedeviling admission processes into higher institutions of learning; leading to admission syndicates and layers of interest groups, all greatly aggravates corruption in southwest institutions in Nigeria. Corruption on admission process do deny best students from getting admitted while those through the back door ends up as a disservice to the nations’ human capital development. This finding is consistent with the findings in previous works of Ogu and Amakwe (2020); Arop, Ekpang, Nwannunu and Owan (2018); Seniwoliba and Boahene (2015).

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concludes that corruption on students' academic performance and corruption on students' admission process further aggravate state of corruption in Southwest higher institutions of learning. This then translate to mean that if corruption practices by players in the academic spheres particularly if corruption on students' academic performance and corruption on students' admission process could be reduced then corruption level in Southwest higher institution of learning will go drastically reduced go down.

Based on the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made;

The study recommends that the South West Governors Forum, NGOS, Ministry of Education at both federal and State level should evolve transparent student academic performance rating system of conference marking as done by Professional examination bodies, whereby body of markers and body of checkers are well compartmentalized while course lecturer's continuous assessment are inputted along. This will reignite spirit of academic competition amount students, it will cut away leverages of lecturer's boys who have formed cartel of extortion and it will also allow the system to rate performances of committed lecturers.

From result emanating from analysis, the study recommends that both Federal and State Government's ministry of Education, Joint Admission Matriculation Board, Higher Institution's ICT centres and NGO's should presents a real time grading system that offers admission to prospecting candidates instead of the delayed admission processing time that encourages speculations and negotiations as such evolved system will rendered chains of admission racketeers useless since admission will be on real time basis devoid of speculation or need for interconnectedness.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Adewale, G. (2014). Examination Malpractice: A Stigma on School Effectiveness in Nigeria. <https://www.unilorin.edu.ng>
- [2] Aniodoh, H. C. O., Ebouh, C. N., & Nweke, J. O. (2017). Academic corruption and students achievements in tertiary institutions in Enugu State. *International Journal of Progressive and Alternative Education*, 4(1), 5-13.
- [3] Arop, F. O., Ekpang, M. A., Nwannunu, B. I., & Owan, V. J. (2018). Personnel management and corrupt academic practices in universities In Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, VI(9), 405-419.
- [4] Asiyai, R. I., & Oghuvbu, E. P. (2020). Prevalent crime in Nigerian tertiary institutions and administrative strategies for its effective management. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 9(2), 270-279.
- [5] Atanda, A. I. (2019). Corrupt practices in tertiary institutions in Nigeria: Management tips towards alleviation of Corruption. *East African Journal of Educational Research and Policy*, 14(1), 277-288.
- [6] Boly, A., Keita, K., Okara A., & Okou, G. C. (2020). Effect of Corruption on Educational Quantity and Quality: Theory and Evidence. A Working Paper No 337 of African Development Bank. Retrieved from <https://www.afdb.org/en/documents/publications/working-paper-series/>
- [7] Idoniboye-Obu, S. A. (2014). Corruption in Higher Education in Nigeria: Prevalence, Structures and Patterns among students of higher education institutions in Nigeria. Being Thesis Submitted in fulfilment of the

requirements for the Doctor of Philosophy degree in Political Science, School of Social Sciences, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Pietermaritzburg Campus, South Africa

- [8] Gallant, T. B., & Drinan, P. (2006). Organizational theory and student cheating: Explanation, responses, and strategies. *The Journal of Higher Education* 77(5), 839-860.
- [9] Graaf, G. De. (2007). Causes of corruption: Towards a contextual theory of corruption. *Public Administration Quarterly*, 31(1/2), 39-86.
- [10] Hallak, J., & Poisson, M. (2007). *Corrupt schools, corrupt universities: what can be done?* Paris: UNESCO & International Institute for Educational Planning. Retrieved, <http://www.unesco.org/iiep>
- [11] Indawati, N. (2015). The Development of Anti-Corruption Education Course for Primary School Teacher Education Students. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(35), 48-54
- [12] Jekayinfa A.A., & Kolawole, D.O. (2010). Conceptual background to the history of education in Nigeria, (Eds) In J.O.O. Abiri and Jekayinfa, A. A. *Perspective on the History of Education in Nigeria*. Ilorin, Kwara state, Bamitex Printing and Publication Enterprise.
- [13] Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(1), 607-610.
- [14] Nwaokugha, D. O., & Ezeugwu, M. C. (2017). Corruption in the education industry in Nigeria, Implications for national development. *European Journal of Training and Development Studies*, 4(1), 1-17.
- [15] Ogu, E. O. P., & Amakwe, E. B. (2020). Combating corruption in Nigeria tertiary institutions: call for change. *World Journal of Innovative Research*, 9(1), 36-46.
- [16] Oko, S. U., & Adie, R. I. (2016). Examination malpractice: Causes, effects and possible ways of curbing the menace. A study of Cross River university of technology. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research*, 4(1), 59-65.
- [17] Okojie, J. (2012, July 24). Corruption had assumed a worrisome level. *Vanguard*. Retrieved from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2012/07/corruption-had-assumed-a-worrisome-level-okojie/>
- [18] Open Society Initiative for West Africa (OSIWA). (2016). Effectiveness of Anti-Corruption Agencies in West Africa Benin, Liberia, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal and Sierra Leone. Retrieved from <https://www.opensocietyfoundations.org/uploads/75e014a3-1b37-4412>
- [19] Romyantseva, N. L. (2005). Taxonomy of corruption in higher education. *Peabody Journal of Education*, 80(1), 81-92.
- [20] Sarmini, I. M. S., & Ulin, N. (2017). The importance of anti corruption education teaching materials for the young generation. *The 2nd International Joint Conference on Science and Technology : Journal of Physics: Conf. Series* doi :10.1088/1742-6596/953/1/012167
- [21] Sen, K. (2015). Governance and development outcomes in Asia. In A. B. Deolalikar, S. Jha, & P. F. Quising, *Governance in developing Asia : Public service delivery and empowerment* (pp. 78-100). Manila.
- [22] Seniwoliba, J. A., & Boahene, B. E. (2015). Manifestation of corruption in higher education: The role of the university administrator. *Direct Research Journal of Social Science and Educational Studies*, 2(3), xx-xx.
- [23] Tella, A. (2008). Teacher variables as predictors of academic achievement of primary school pupils mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 1(1).
- [24] Transparency International. (2013). *Global Corruption Report: Education*. New York: Routledge.
- [25] Transparency International (2020). *Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI)*. Available at <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2020/index/nga#>
- [26] Uzochukwu, M. (2015). Examination Malpractice and Causes. <http://uzochukwumike.Hubpages>.
- [27] Whawo, D. D. (2015). A study of corrupt practices in tertiary institutions in Delta State Of Nigeria . *Journal of Education, Arts and Humanities*, 3(2), 22-28.
- [28] Wibowo, A. P., & dan Puspito, N. T. (2011). *Peranan Mahasiswa dalam Pencegahan Korupsi. Dalam Pendidikan Anti Korupsi untuk Perguruan Tinggi/ Anti Korupsi*. Jakarta: Kemendikbud